

The Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in the New Normal

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Abstract:- Management in the new normal is an inventiveness to adopt new drift in the education system. Thus, this research study purposely to examine the Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in this progression of new normal living condition. A qualitative research approach particularly a Case Study design was utilized. The population of this study were focused on the Seven (7) Deans of Criminal Justice Education of various Universities and Colleges and a Semi Structured Interview employing the open ended questions was utilized in order to extract more discussion on the Management and Challenges of the different deans, guided by the ethical principles on research. The results found out two challenges in the new normal; the Flexible and Remote Learning and Blended Learning Modalities. Intervention approach was also identified like the Work Home Status, Asynchronous and Synchronous Study Learning and Social Media plat forms. Indeed, the management of Deans is immediately needed in this challenging time like; lack of new computer skills, Academic freedom of teachers regarding poor performances of students, the duties and responsibilities of the personnel towards clientele.

Keywords:- Management and Challenges, New Normal, Criminology Deans, Blended Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the route of the pandemic, human beings went from saying “I can’t wait for things to go back to normal” to asking “Will things go back to normal?” it seems that at last were accepting it as a “new normal” – That’s not bad. It won’t be the same as in 2019 or early 2020. As our personal and professional way of life changes dramatically, some necessary adjustments will be needed. But there are opportunities for this change.

Both personally and professionally, pandemics have that benefit. On the personal side, the pandemic encouraged people to make significant lifestyle changes. According to a survey conducted by the Cleveland Clinic and Parade, 62% of people have changed their lifestyle. People report spending more time outside and in nature, starting or changing exercise programs, improving sleep patterns, and making other health-conscious dietary changes. In addition, 34% of respondents say they have a healthier diet, and 87% of those people say they continue their habits.

People who used to travel constantly for work now have the option of staying home with their families and holding many meetings via phone or video conference. Also, people are more willing to digital conferencing than they were before the pandemic. Employees working from home can save on greenhouse gas emissions. In the United States, remote employees save about 3.6 million tonnes of greenhouse gases each year by avoiding commuting. Digital communications are better than ever because companies have to make changes and do them well. Today, businesses understand the need to be agile and effective online. Pandemics show everyone how quickly things change and the importance of digital tools for business success. Companies are ready to act quickly when needed.

The most important things we can all do now are open, open to change, open to others. The pandemic has revealed that it is terrible in itself, that we are all human beings and that we are only doing our best. Whether or not you make a positive move during a pandemic (like everyone who reports healthy changes and stronger family ties), it’s never too late to take advantage of it. .. The new normal has many advantages. Just as you don’t need access to the gym to start your fitness routine, you don’t necessarily need an office to succeed at work. For businesses, the benefits of remote working and new digital skills offer the opportunity to reduce costs and increase productivity. Kevin Leyes (2022)

COVID-19 has become a new problem in education worldwide. From the paper of Elton Ishaq (2022). This survey aims to investigate the challenges faced by schools during the New Normal era, especially in Central Java. This issue is related to educational and learning strategies during a pandemic by adopting an educational risk management model in new normal scenarios.

From academic studies of teachers who have encountered many challenges caused by the outbreak of COVID-19. 10 teachers from 5 junior high schools in the Philippines who participated voluntarily. Thematic findings show that these teachers have serious problems with pandemics in terms of quality communication, module distribution and recall, student difficulty in following instructions, power outages, internet connectivity, and health risks. Showed that you are facing. Therefore, educators need to be prepared for all possible situations. It is unlikely that this situation will improve soon. Instead, teachers need to adapt and accept this reality. Aina Joyce D. Agayon, Et.AL. (2022)

Dafan Shu (2016). The ideological and political education of college students is influenced by "New Normal" such as diversification of social ideological trend, new media application, and integration of ideological and political education system of college students, Meanwhile in the study conducted by Martin P. Paulus, MD^{1,2}; and Wesley K. Thompson, PhD³ (2019). They emphasize that explanations and accurate predictions are the fundamental deliverables for a mechanistic or pragmatic approach that academic psychiatric research can provide to stakeholders.

Finally, Steve Brammer and Timothy Clark (2020) has stipulated in their recent study that When COVID-19 emerged in January and February 2020, the impact on universities and BS reflected the pattern of grades and the concentration of cases in a few countries (China, Japan, South Korea). .. As a result, outbreaks increased exponentially in all countries, and their impact extended to include all campus education, international student activities, and pastoral support. COVID-19 also influenced student recruitment and sought to maintain financial sustainability during the crisis. BS quickly adapted pedagogy and assessment. Currently, BS is considering more planned and structured adaptations. "new normal".

To relate this study, the researchers would like to determine if what are the Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in this progression of new normal living condition.

❖ *Statement of the Problem;*

1. What are the Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in the new normal?
2. What are the Intervention programs by the Criminology Deans among the Challenges in the new normal?

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the local related literature of management and challenges of criminology deans in the new normal, Determining the impact of civilian review board on the police is a challenging process (De Guzman & Frank, 2004). The extent of compliance of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology Program on the Policies and Standards prescribed by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (Habitan, E.N., 2020). Buenviaje, M.G Et. Al.,(2017) on their study "Leader Motivating Language Affecting Faculty Members' Work Performance from a Private Academic Institution in the Philippines" assert that the Motivating Language Theory that faculty members can be encouraged to perform their work assignments better. It is argued that planning professionals need to consider and understand this new perspective for safer and sustainable cities, rather than relying on assumptions that are not supported by any systematic evidence (Cozens, P.M. 2011). Another challenges of Deans is the safety of the studentry in times of calamity, wherein The participation of youth in any disaster risk reduction activities could be enhanced when they have high levels of awareness on climate change (Barreda, A. 2018) another is the practice of school-based random student

drug testing (RSDT) as part of an overall drug prevention strategy among higher education (Dupont, R.L, Et. Al.,2012).

III. MANAGEMENT AND CHALLENGESE OF CRIMINOLOGY DEAN'S IN THE NEW NORMAL

In pursuance of an outcomes-based quality assurance system as advocated under CHED Memorandum Order no. 46, series 2012, entitled Policy Standards to Quality Assurance in the Philippines Higher Education through an Outcome-Based and Typology-Based Quality Assurance and by Virtue of Commission en Banc Resolution No. 467-2017, the Criminology Program under state universities and colleges (SUCs) and local universities and Colleges (LUC) are provided ample space to innovate in their curriculum an assessment how to achieve learning outcomes in their particular contexts and their respective mission. Anent on this mandate, at present the SUCs and LUCs are challenge to ensure the continuity of teaching and learning via virtual methods or other teaching modes in delivering education especially to far flunk areas where net is inconvenient. Thus this work task is Criminology dean's accountability to design a teaching paradigm suited to meet institution objectives of bringing their students at par and competitive with other SUCs and LUCs product in delivering efficient and effective services in crime prevention, crime detection and investigation, law enforcement, public safety, custody, and rehabilitation of the offenders, criminological research and among others despite of our pressing crisis situation today brought by this Covid 19. Thus, to make this happened, it is again a dean's office accountability to prepare a meeting to the faculty and staff, students and to the different members of the community for them to adjust in their new accountability to make the new situation normal. For the outcomes of this meeting reach the higher learning institution admin office, the dean's office must design a strategic action plan which convey all involve parties desire especially for grades, time and finance adjustment.

The paradigm below encapsulates a management plan replacing the old education management system into new practical paradigm suited to meet the new normal situation in guiding the students for them to meet their future expectation as they will be done in their studies. On it, the outside arrows connect the institution management while the inside arrows connect the dean management bringing education via various social media platforms closer to the students in their respective communities. Wherein, through these social media platforms the college faculty members and staff maintain the college dean management sustaining the delivery of education in the community despite of the new normal situation now a day.

To further understand the discussion cited above, below are the paradigm of the study on "The Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in the new normal, A Case Study" As shown Below,

Fig 1. Paradigm of the study

IV. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design and methodology, population of the study, Prospect Proponent, Data Gathering Instrument

➤ *Research Design and Methodology*

A qualitative research approach particularly a Case Study design were used to this study. A case study is an in-depth study of a particular research problem rather than a sweeping statistical survey or comprehensive comparative inquiry. It is often used to narrow down a very broad field of research into one or a few easily researchable examples. The case study research design is also useful for testing whether a specific theory and model actually applies to phenomena in the real world. It is a useful design when not much is known about an issue or phenomenon (De Vaus, 2006).

➤ *Prospect Proponent*

The population of this study are focused on the Seven (7) Criminal Justice Education Deans of various Universities and Colleges. Further, a consent form prior to participating and promise and ensure that their identity will be kept confidential.

➤ *Data Gathering Instrument*

The data will be gathered using a Semi Structured Interview employing the open ended questions was utilized in order to extract more discussion on the Management and Challenges of the different deans. it generally means a one-to-one interview on one general topic, which is covered in detail. Usually, these qualitative interviews last about an hour, although sometimes much longer. It sounds like two people having a discussion, but there are differences in the power dynamics, and end goal: for the classic sociologist Burgess (2002) these are “conversations with a purpose”.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedure*

The researcher has seek the advice and approval of the Dean of the Criminal Justice Education of the University of the Cordilleras, Baguio City to prepare and execute a letter for the conduct of the study to the School Administrator of the Institution where the Deans as our Participants, after the approval of this research proposal, the researcher conducted a data gathering by means of in-depth interview. All interviews will be recorded. The interviews were informal and with the use of open-ended question, and carried out in a conversational style.

The researcher wrote in detail the result of the interviews, follow-up interviews, observations, and casual encounters with the participants. Notes were also being written while listening to recorded interviews, typing transcripts, and reflecting upon a particular interview. In addition to the interviews and follow-up interviews, the researcher obtained other data throughout the study, such as added valuable information having great value on the study with the participants.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

This study was guided by the ethical principles on research. The research ethics was focused on requirements of voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality and the personal safety of the participants and the researcher.

The participants of this study are not force nor coerce to participate in this study. They can decline to answer the question for any reason. They can also withdraw their participation in this research verbally and/or return the unfinished questionnaire to the researcher. Debriefing were also conducted to stabilize the psychological condition of the participants. Moreover, strict confidentiality and anonymity of the participants are always observing and maintain. Lastly, no money was given to the participants however, token of appreciation was considered.

➤ *Treatment of Data*

To treat the qualitative data, a thematic analysis by Creswell (2018) has utilized by the researcher. Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It is usually applied to a set of texts; such as interview transcripts. The researcher closely examined the data to identify common themes – topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Part I. The Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in the new normal.

➤ *Technology Gadgets for Flexible and Remote Learning*

In the part of the interviewed participants, the Deans mostly stated that they became tricky on the “flexible and remote learning” due to the new approaches that they run into and has implemented in their management. Participants 2, 4, and 5 has said that, “Hi-Technology Gadgets like laptops and cellular phones were the most problems they encountered among students and teachers in the conduct of their

instructions”, their lack of skills on navigation made them problematic on how they cope up with the new style of learning. The Internet Connectivity was a prevalent hindrance in the conduct of their classes which resulted in the part of the students who underwent part time jobs to acquire an additional cash backing to satisfy their Data connectivity and or Wi-Fi-connection aside from what they receive from their sponsors like parents, guardians and possible grants due to financial constraint effected by the pandemic. Meanwhile, according to our interview with the participants, some teachers from public universities and colleges through the initiatives of their deans were provided with quality Wi-Fi with high and strong MBPS in order to deliver effectively their services to their clientele, but despite of this good solution given by their institution aiming to reach their students regularly most of the students’ side were complaining due to poor net-connectivity and often time power interruption particularly to students who were at remote places. Both Teachers and Students were complaining with the instability of Net-Connectivity as the scenario which is resulting into dissatisfactions of the conducted classes, students who were at the other side of laptops and Cellular phones were off-cameras oftentimes and the teachers really do not know if they are participating in their classes or not because they indeed do not know if the signal was really poor or they are just doing an alibi to escape their classes, all of the sudden, the students are claiming by heart that they were open with their cameras if their attention were called too. Lastly, some students were also complaining to their teachers due to their strictness on attendances and the punctuality observance in passing their online requirements which even reach the office of the president of the affected institution and the Commission on Higher Education of their respective regions regarding this matter. The participant deans were the often-problematic individuals in the emergence of these problems in this new-normal era caused by this Covid 19 Pandemic.

As schools and universities everywhere suffer from the effects of COVID-19, researching efficient ways to continue education is an urgent task. Education experts and managers talked about flexible learning and distance learning. These have been regarded as solutions for providing education in the era of pandemics. Flexible learning is a learner-centered approach where students can choose the pace, place, and mode of delivery of their lessons. Remote learning is a part of flexible learning and is only one of many delivery modes that instructors can choose from, depending on the needs and context of the students and the courses that they teach. University of the Philippines, Los Banos (2020)

➤ *Blended Learning Modalities*

The participants Deans 1, 2, 7 has observed the obvious booming of students’ academic scholars in the college of Criminal Justice Education and so with the very few student drop-outs. According to their answers with our interviews, these were indeed the possible outcome of the introduced new school learning method which is the “*blended learning modalities*,” because the Commission on Higher Education has issued memorandums to harmonize the policies on education since the pandemic covid 19 indeed struck everyone that has ended many people to be weakened from

all kinds of activities wherein schooling is included. The “*blended learning modalities*” according to the participants as scholarly introduced by both Dep-Ed and CHED has aimed to respect the students in their rights to education through their parents to provides various distance learning modalities that are suited to the location of the learners. Parents are the ones who decide the applicable learning modality for their children in order to avoid the possible immediate dropping out of the teachers to their students due to their strict checking of attendances and huge school requirements. That therefore, the Commission on Higher Education reminds the Higher Institutions through the school authorities whom they include our participants to possibly give all the necessary program solutions in order to avoid the dropping out of the students caused by the negative effects of the pandemic such as financial crisis in the parts of parents and guardians who were affected by the continual lockdowns of the locality where they reside and the forced closing-up of companies or agencies where they worked that resulted from their untimely insolvency. That, the teachers through CHED Memorandums cannot just make an incomplete mark and neither failing grade to any student by reasons of no computer technology gadgets, poor internet connectivity, virtual and non-virtual absences or even late or non-passing at all of requirements, non-performance of activities and other related school requirements needed to satisfy their grades. Being passive teacher to higher authorities and the giving of passing grade to these students who encountered such problems is of great help in order to resolve these education obstacles towards the affected students on the matter amidst to pandemic. The academic freedom of teachers during this unfriendly phenomenon became silent and humane to the clientele in general.

The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic affects the delivery of lessons to learners. It paves the way to have new approaches in teaching and learning. The Department of Education (DepEd) provides various distance learning modalities that are suited to the location of the learners. Parents are the ones who decide the applicable learning modality for their children. A survey conducted by the DepEd revealed that most of the parents prefer to have a modular distance learning modality. Learning modules are provided by the schools for the learners. However, some of the parents prefer to combine the learning modules with the online explanation of the teachers regarding the content of the lessons. This is classified under blended learning or the combination of online and modular learning modalities. In this condition, teachers meet their learners at least once a week using Google Meet. Their primary task is to explain the content of their lessons and to address the queries of the learners. Likewise, teachers are going to distribute and retrieve copies of the learning modules to/from the learners. Isagani Canonizado (2021)

Part II. The Intervention programs by the Criminology Deans among the Challenges in the new normal.

➤ *Work Home Status*

All the participants have answered and agreed, that monitoring their personnel under “*work home status*” is really challenging and hard one. That both faculty and staff during the height of Covid Pandemic were given at least Two Days (2) days’ work home, two (2) days physical duty reports and one (1) day sanitation and cleaning observation per week in their respective institutions except when times of hard lockdowns wherein it does not really warrant the situation. Covid-IATF protocols were always considered all the times especially to open and public places where possible virus be absorbed by any rate to any would be victim. The employees of their colleges or departments were given the task to undertake as a form of requirements in checking their attendances and work output such as: accomplishment reports with attached photographs of virtual classes, held quizzes, activities, major examinations results and accomplished Daily Time Record (DTR) duly scrutinized and evaluated by their respective Deans. Consequently, and according to some participants, dedications and honesty were their self-convinced policy in the conduct of checking the professionalism on the services of their subordinates in the actual realization of their oath duties and responsibilities towards their clientele. Meanwhile, realizing this intervention program is still dependent on the pleasure of the top management if what particular days would be scheduled to satisfy the said given schedules in-order to minimize the escalation amidst to Covid 19 Pandemic as the case maybe.

When working from home, there may be a new concern for workers other than going without pants. To ensure employees do what they’re supposed to, some employers have begun using surveillance apps and programs to monitor worker productivity. This has raised some worker privacy concerns and the questions of whether this is legal or proper. The short answer is that yes, it can be legal if done right. As for whether it’s proper or not, that’s up to debate. In this article, I’ll discuss what can or cannot be done when it comes to employers remotely supervising their employees. Tom Spiggle (2020).

➤ *Asynchronous and Synchronous Study Learning*

The cooperative participants accepted, agreed and explained that during this pandemic situation this kind of education program in the school is quite worthy into many aspects. First of all, it is one way of helping our government to effectively lessen if not totally eradicate the Covid Virus Pandemic contaminating the big number of the populace resulting into millions of deaths among victims. That the participants used both of the classroom resources depending on the call of the Top Management of the School as they based it usually from the Covid-IATF orders in order to avoid direct violations from the pandemic policies. The participants of this study also revealed that the “*Asynchronous and Synchronous Study Learning*” were both utilized in the teaching modality, asynchronous learning is observed when the level of pandemic is at high risk while synchronous learning when the alert level of risk of the pandemic situation

is at low level. Mostly, during the usage of synchronous learning the students were also eased from various loads of struggles brought by concentrations of their studies and the stressful effect of the deadly virus. Further, the academicians were also professionally informed and persuaded by the academic management to become lenient from understanding the students regarding their performances in their academic standing and not limited on the giving of considerations to accept late passing of requirements, projects, activities and the like, or the humane giving of extension considerations for those students who maybe late in responding their school matters and obligations to assure their parts not to get low on grades or a failing grade due to pandemic adverse effect regarding their academic performances.

The terms “synchronous” and “asynchronous” learning have become ubiquitous in describing online learning although they similarly exist in in-person learning environments. Synchronous learning refers to instructors and students gathering at the same time and (virtual or physical) place and interacting in “real-time”. Asynchronous learning refers to students accessing materials at their own pace and interacting with each other over longer period. Sandford Graduate School for Education (2022)

➤ *Social Media plat forms*

The coming of the Covid 19 pandemic was the start of new trend on education. Different modalities were introduced to meet up the academic needs of the students wherever them in the country so long that internet connectivity will reach them. The participants of the study consistently agreed and shared to us the big role of “*social media platforms*” in the rendering of learning towards our students clientele, but because of the bold scenario that most of our teaching forces are quite unequipped with the technological knowledge of using the different social media programs or apps in the computer learning then their respective schools through the initiative of their Criminal Justice Education Deans and other authorities in the academic instructions of their institutions have established a continues and consistent programs on trainings and seminars on computer learning educations which are focus on the apps that are suited and correspondingly needed in the medium of instruction among teachers who would handle the subjects. The participants indeed accept the hardship of coping up the modern learning styles especially so that the traditional use of black and white boards really existed since immemorial time, admittedly, they cannot just throw them outright since they were used to utilized them as part of their strategies, source of strengths and enthusiasms as they go on discussing their ready topics before their students sitting in front of them and ready to stand when called upon during class interaction and brainstorming. The used of spreadsheet in computing their grades, the Edmodo in having their examinations, the google link for their quizzes, the google meet and via-zoom for virtual classes, cup-cat for video recording, advance words, PowerPoint presentation, computer command short-cut methods and other significant social media platforms were the few introduced computer technology knowledges and skills amongst respective educators who underwent the said trainings and seminars.

The ubiquity of social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, messenger) is no more apparent than at the university. Social media are increasingly visible in higher education settings as instructors look to technology to mediate and enhance their instruction as well as promote active learning for students. Many scholars argue for the purposeful integration of social media as an educational tool. Empirical evidence, however, has lagged in supporting the claim. Most of the existing research on the utility and effectiveness of social media in the higher education class is limited to self-reported data (e.g., surveys, questionnaires) and content analyses. This paper summarizes the scholarly writings as well as reviews the findings of empirical investigations. Some limitations are discussed, and future areas of research are proposed. Paul A. Tess (2013)

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it concluded that “The Management and Challenges of Criminology Deans in the new normal.”

1. Is indeed complicated due to lack of new computer skills navigations in the part of students and teachers and likewise the needed academic hi-technology gadgets, poor internet connectivity and power interruptions.
2. Academic freedom of teachers regarding poor performances of students that may result into failing grades caused by the pandemic details became silent and humane among the clientele affected by this unfriendly phenomenon.
3. The duties and responsibilities of the personnel towards clientele were religiously checked by the Deans despite of the challenges amidst to Covid 19 pandemic, dedication and honesty to service and duty is highly observe among academicians.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. A Trainings and seminars on the new trend, applications and navigations of social media platforms are highly recommended among academicians and student clientele.
2. A need for a Subsidy backing for school gadgets and finances is needed among poor but deserving students when time of deadly pandemic.
3. A work from home arrangement must be continue to enforce, however, output of faculty must be strictly monitored by the Dean concerned.

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